

Preliminary Sensitivity Analysis for Control Rod Worth by Homogenized Macroscopic Cross Section Perturbation

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803801

ABSTRACT

The calculation uncertainty of reactor physics parameters is determined and validated by comparing with the results of reactor physics tests or critical experiments. The test for control rod worth is usually carried out under zero power condition of beginning of cycle. It is questionable whether the control rod worth under other conditions is within the uncertainty range of the calculated worth when control rod worth satisfies the acceptance criteria in the test condition. Since it is nearly impossible to measure reactor physics parameters including control rod worth under various conditions, it is necessary to perform numerical experiments. Numerical tests were performed by perturbing homogenized macroscopic cross sections used in diffusion nodal calculation. This paper provides the test results of individual control rod group worth and the N-1 control rod worth under zero power conditions.

Keywords: control rod worth, uncertainty, reactor physics test, macroscopic cross section perturbation

1. INTRODUCTION

The reactor physics parameters such as control rod worth (CRW) and temperature reactivity coefficients are the basis of safety analysis of postulated accident (PA) or anticipated operational occurrence (AOO). Safety analysis uses conservative value of reactor physics parameters considering their calculation uncertainties, which is determined by comparing with the measured results of reactor physics tests or critical experiments. The reactor physics test is usually carried out under zero power condition at the beginning of cycle (BOC), which is different from PA or AOO condition. Thus, it is questionable whether the uncertainty of reactor physics parameters under other conditions is within the uncertainty range of the calculated value when test result satisfies the acceptance criteria under the test condition. Since it is nearly impossible to measure reactor physics parameters under PA or AOO conditions, numerical experiments need to be considered to verify the validity of the calculated uncertainty.

This paper focuses on the sensitivity analysis of the CRW. The reactor physics tests for pressurized water reactors (PWRs) usually need to comply with test procedures and acceptance criteria written in ANSI/ANS-19.6.1 [1]. Three test methods, which are boron exchange method (BEM), rod swap test method (RSM), and dynamic rod worth test method (DRWM), are used to measure the CRW and acceptance criteria for individual group worth and the sum of individual group worth are given in the reference. Due to differences in test conditions, the reference CRW which is the result of calculation may vary depending on the test method. As a result, even if the acceptance criteria are satisfied by one method, it is possible that measured CRW with other methods is not in acceptable criteria. Moreover,

N-1 CRW, which means the CRW of all control rods except the one with the highest worth and is one of the most important parameters in safety analysis, is not exactly same as the sum of the individual control rod group worth. The purpose of this paper is to evaluate that each measurement method provides consistent CRW difference, which is base of the uncertainty of CRW.

Since it is not straightforward to configure numerical experiment rigorously, simple numerical experiment using homogenized macroscopic cross section perturbation was considered as a preliminary approach. The PARCS code [2], which is a part of the nuclear design audit tools of Korea Institute of Nuclear Safety (KINS) and intended to be used for multi-physics calculation by coupling with the FAMILY code [3][4], is used for numerical experiments with homogenized cross sections produced by POLARIS/TRITON of SCALE code [5].

2. CONTROL ROD WORTH CALCULATION

The BEM, RSM, and DRWM are often used in the CRW measurement in PWRs. The initial conditions for BEM and DRWM are all control rod out (ARO) except that the lead control rod group is slightly inserted. Thus, the reactivity under ARO condition is slightly positive. The CRW is measured by inserting the test group (TG) of control rod from the ARO condition to the bottom position. During the test with BEM, soluble boron concentration (SBC) changes continuously to compensate reactivity by control rod insertion with discrete motion as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Reactivity change during boron dilution and control rod insertion for BEM

The reactivity change in each insertion step ($\Delta\rho_i$), which can be calculated as Eq.(1), is measured by reactivity computer, and the total reactivity is calculated as a sum of each reactivity change, written as Eq.(2).

$$\Delta\rho_i = \rho(h_{i+}, SBC_i) - \rho(h_{i-}, SBC_i), \quad (1)$$

$$\rho_{BEM} = \sum \Delta\rho_i, \quad (2)$$

where h is the inserted length of TG and i is the index of the discrete control rod insertion, and SBC_i is SBC when i 'th rod insertion was performed. It has been observed that there is little reactivity dependence on the soluble boron concentration. Eq.(2) can be approximated as following :

$$\rho_{BEM} \approx \rho(H, \overline{SBC}) - \rho(0, \overline{SBC}), \quad (3)$$

where H is the fully inserted length and \overline{SBC} is the average SBC during boron exchange. For DRWM, the SBC does not change. Thus, Eq.(4) was used to calculate CRW with DRWM.

$$\rho_{DRWM} = \rho(H) - \rho(0), \quad (4)$$

The reference group (RG) for the rod swap test needs to be tested by BEM. Thus, the initial condition is that the reactor is critical with RG at the bottom position, while other groups are at the top position. For the RSM, SBC does not change and the RG is withdrawn to maintain critical as TG is inserted. Since the control rod group with the highest worth is selected as RG, RG is partially inserted when TG is fully inserted. Eq.(5) was used to calculate CRW with RSM.

$$\rho_{RSM} = \rho_{TGin}(h_{RG}) - \rho_{TGout}(h_{RG}), \quad (5)$$

where h_{RG} is the critical height of RG when TG is fully inserted and ρ_{in} and ρ_{out} are reactivity when TG is fully inserted and withdrawn, respectively.

When reactor trips, all control rods are inserted by gravity. For conservative analysis, the control rod with highest worth is usually assumed to be stuck. Thus, the N-1 CRW is considered in safety analysis of PAs and AOOs. The stuck rod needs to be selected to minimize the N-1 CRW, and is not always same. Thus, N-1 CRW can be calculated as Eq.(6).

$$\rho_{N-1} = \max\{\rho_i - \rho_0\}, \quad (6)$$

where ρ_i is the calculated reactivity when all control rods except i 'th control rod are inserted, and ρ_0 is the calculated reactivity when all control rods are withdrawn. ρ_{N-1} is selected as maximum value since ρ_i is negative and ρ_0 is usually zero (critical) in the normal ARO operation.

The meet N-1 CRW assumed in safety analysis, measured CRW needs to be greater than the lower bound of CRW, considering uncertainty. Unlike the N-1 CRW, the measured CRW needs to be less than the upper bound of CRW for particular conditions such as the control rod ejection accident (REA). Since the CRW of single control rod assembly is not measured during reactor physics tests, the uncertainty needs to be confirmed by the measurement of the CRW of individual control rod group.

3. MACROSCOPIC CROSS SECTION PERTURBATION

It is known that there is a difference between calculated and measured results of reactor physics parameters, even with continuous energy Monte Carlo calculation, which is considered as the most accurate calculation. The difference may be caused by nuclear data, geometrical modelling, measurement uncertainty, and so on. If the diffusion nodal method is considered, the discrepancy can occur due to additional uncertainties in nodal methodology and homogenized cross sections. However, the real reactor core is different from a simplified model such as a single assembly lattice problem,

which relies on given nuclear data library which has inherent uncertainty. Thus, the macroscopic cross section set used in the diffusion nodal calculation has the uncertainty.

The macroscopic homogenized group constants usually calculated with following equation.

$$\Sigma_{x,g} = \sum_i N_i \frac{\sum_m \sigma_{i,x,g} \phi_{m,g} V_m}{\sum_m \phi_{m,g} V_m}, \quad (7)$$

where N_i is the number density of i 'th isotope, g is the index of energy group, and x is the reaction type. The macroscopic homogenized cross section with Eq.(7) generally condensed into smaller groups for diffusion nodal calculations. The nuclear data itself has uncertainty which depends on material, reaction and energy group. Since Eq.(7) is the result of the single assembly calculation, the scalar flux might has uncertainty depends on the computational mesh and the energy group. The group constant Including uncertainty can be written as Eq.(8).

$$\Sigma_{x,g} + \delta\Sigma_{x,g} = \sum_i N_i \frac{\sum_m (\sigma_{i,x,g} + \delta\sigma_{i,x,g}) (\phi_{m,g} + \delta\phi_{m,g}) V_m}{\sum_m (\phi_{m,g} + \delta\phi_{m,g}) V_m}, \quad (8)$$

where $\delta\Sigma_{x,g}$, $\delta\sigma_{i,x,g}$, and $\delta\phi_{m,g}$ are uncertainties of macroscopic cross section, microscopic cross section, and scalar flux, respectively.

The reactor core is usually designed with 1/8 symmetry and the fuel assemblies in symmetric positions, which have same material property, temperature and scalar flux, are expected to have same uncertainty on nuclear data and scalar flux. Thus, the uncertainty of group constant is function of FA position of the core, reaction type, and energy group.

If the macroscopic cross section difference is the sole source of the discrepancy between the results of measurement and calculation, the uncertainty analysis of reactor physics parameters can be performed using the uncertainty of the macroscopic cross section uncertainty, $\delta\Sigma_{x,g}$. The numerical experiments with the macroscopic cross section perturbation are motivated by this assumption. The calculation results with the homogenized cross section obtained by lattice calculation (RX, reference cross section) are treated as design values, while those with perturbed cross section (PX) are regarded as the measured values. Since a rigorous perturbation methodology is not straightforward to implement, a simplified perturbation scheme with arbitrarily selected variations is adopted in this study.

PARCS code, which uses transport, absorption, fission, scattering cross sections for diffusion nodal calculation, is used for numerical experiments. Each type and energy group of cross section might be perturbed differently. To remove complexity, only perturbation on absorption cross section is considered. Since transport, absorption and fission are related, their cross sections need to be adjusted. If perturbation of absorption cross section is as in Eq.(9),

$$\delta\Sigma_a = \alpha\Sigma_a, \quad (9)$$

where Σ_a is homogenized absorption cross section calculated by lattice code and α is random number within given tolerance. The tolerance is arbitrarily assumed to 10% in this work. Same α is used both in fast and thermal energy for simplicity. The transport cross section is adjusted to the amount of change

of absorption cross section and the fission cross section is adjusted as same ratio with absorption cross section as in Eq.(10).

$$\delta\Sigma_{tr} = \alpha\Sigma_a, \quad \delta\Sigma_f = \alpha\Sigma_f. \quad (10)$$

The derivatives of cross section for fuel temperature, moderator temperature, moderator density, and soluble boron concentration also need to be adjusted. For simple test, derivatives are adjusted in same way with Eqs.(9)-(10). Different random numbers are used for each fuel assembly of 1/8 core.

4. Numerical Results

The test problem is based on the initial core of the APR1400 [6], which consists of 241 fuel assemblies. The hot zero power with no xenon is used in the calculation. Each numerical test was conducted with 38 random numbers for fuel assemblies considering 1/8 symmetry as shown in Figure 2. The control rod group map is also shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. 1/8 Core (38FAs) and Control Rod Group Map of APR1400

A total of 100 random sets were generated for BEM, DRWM, and RSM to evaluate individual control rod groups. For RSM, the reference group was determined using BEM. The assumed residual reactivity (ARO condition) was 30 pcm for BEM and 70 pcm for DRWM. Shutdown rod groups with large worth were divided into subgroups with smaller worth. In total, 14 control rod groups (5 regulating groups and 9 subgroups of two shutdown groups) were considered. The sum of individual group worths was compared with the N-1 CRW. The designed worth corresponds to the unperturbed case (all random numbers set to zero). Two RSM cases were considered: one using Eq. (5) with RX (RSMR), and the other using PX (RSMP). Although CRWs under perturbed conditions are calculated in the RSMP case, they are effectively measured as RSMR values, since RSM measures only the critical height and computes CRW using the reference (RX) condition.

Table I summarizes the CRW results for individual groups. For each method, the mean and twice the standard deviation (2σ) of the difference from the reference are presented. The mean represents bias,

while 2σ represents uncertainty in the calculated design value. In the absence of bias, the mean is expected to approach zero as the number of samples increases. With 100 samples, the mean values are below 3%. The uncertainties (2σ) are 6–18% for BEM and DRWM, 6–30% for RSMP, and 0–6% for RSMR. In reactor physics tests, allowable CRW deviation is $\pm 15\%$ or ± 100 pcm. Groups 6 and 7 exhibit relatively large percentage uncertainties; however, their small absolute worth results in differences only slightly exceeding 100 pcm. Therefore, the assumed 10% random perturbation appears to produce CRWs within a realistic uncertainty range.

Table I. Summary of CRW difference(%) of the Individual CRW from 100 calculations

CR group	BEM		DRWM		RSMP		RSMR	
	Mean	2σ	Mean	2σ	Mean	2σ	Mean	2σ
1	0.03	8.91	-0.01	8.87	RG	-	RG	-
2	1.07	8.80	1.00	8.82	1.11	7.20	-0.10	2.25
3	-0.09	11.39	-0.18	11.33	-0.41	15.11	-0.28	1.65
4	0.72	13.25	0.60	13.26	0.64	9.78	0.10	4.43
5	-0.60	11.07	-0.77	11.05	0.36	18.90	0.62	2.74
6	1.77	17.92	1.65	17.74	2.46	30.62	0.09	6.02
7	1.80	17.92	1.65	17.74	2.43	30.60	0.06	5.99
8	-0.93	9.62	-1.02	9.59	-0.81	9.05	0.26	2.31
9	-0.92	9.61	-1.04	9.58	-0.81	9.03	0.27	2.32
10	0.21	6.52	0.12	6.49	0.17	6.35	0.03	0.65
11	0.21	6.52	0.14	6.48	0.16	6.34	0.03	0.64
12	-1.74	11.73	-1.83	11.77	-2.17	14.87	-0.20	2.26
13	0.33	14.90	0.27	14.93	0.30	10.83	0.27	5.49
14	-1.73	11.74	-1.82	11.78	-2.17	14.86	-0.20	2.24

Since the influence of SBC is expected to be small, BEM and DRWM, which share similar test conditions, show only minor differences. Figures 3 and 4 present the CRW differences from the reference case for each measurement method. Because DRWM yields results very similar to BEM, and some shutdown control rod (CR) subgroups form symmetric pairs, those results are omitted from the figures.

The individual CRW results of BEM and RSMP exhibit similar trends, except for CR5 and CR6, which have relatively small worths (less than 300 pcm). In contrast, the RSMR results show a different pattern with relatively small deviations from the reference condition. This suggests that although individual control rod groups may display similar CRW trends under different reactor conditions (e.g., ARO and partially inserted RG conditions), the measured CRW can differ significantly. The sum of the individual CRWs also does not appear to correlate clearly with the N-1 CRW. Based on the 100 numerical experiments, CRW uncertainty may be evaluated differently depending on the measurement method, and the sum of individual CRWs may not be sufficient to determine the uncertainty of the N-1 CRW.

However, it is difficult to conclude that conventional CRW measurement and uncertainty evaluation methods are invalid, since the perturbation scheme adopted in this study is highly simplified. A more realistic analysis would be considerably more complex. Further studies using more sophisticated perturbation methodologies are required to improve the understanding of CRW uncertainty analysis.

It should also be noted that conventional CRW methodologies may not be directly applicable to advanced reactor designs, such as soluble-boron-free small modular reactors (SMRs). Even if conventional measurement approaches are limited, CRW measurements remain necessary for uncertainty evaluation. Additional numerical experiments with more realistic assumptions, or alternative analytical approaches, are needed to assess the validity of the measurement methods.

Figure 3. Individual CRW difference results of BEM and RSM

Figure 4. Sum of individual CRW and N-1 CRW difference results of BEM and RSM

5. CONCLUSIONS

Numerical tests of CRW using BEM, DRWM, and RSM were performed based on simple macroscopic cross-section perturbations with arbitrarily selected random variations as a preliminary approach. As expected, BEM and DRWM produced very similar results. Although BEM and RSM exhibited broadly similar trends with differences of a few percent, the CRW measured by RSM can deviate significantly from that obtained by BEM. The N-1 CRW, which is practically difficult to measure directly, does not show a clear correlation with the sum of individual CRWs. Since the numerical tests were conducted under simplified assumptions, the results presented in this paper cannot be considered conclusive. Further studies employing more realistic and sophisticated methodologies are required to validate CRW uncertainty evaluations, particularly for advanced reactor designs where conventional CRW measurement methods may not be directly applicable.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the nuclear safety research program through the Korean Foundation of Nuclear Safety (KOFONS), granted financial resource from the Nuclear Safety and Security Commission (NSSC), Republic of KOREA (Grant No. 2106002)

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